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STRATEGIES TO INDIA'S ENGINEERING SECTOR: MARKET OVERVIEW AND FUTURE OUTLOOK

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Abstract

The Present Study Provides an In depth reflections on the emerging market over view and the future outlook for India's strategies to Engineering Sector in the light of Prime Minister Narendra Modi's vision to transform Indian Manufacturing sector towards a policy orientation to “make in India”. The Paper is organise into three section. Section I presents the introductory part of the study, while section II examines some of the emerging issues that India's Engineering sector needs to be promoted as a strategies for innovational research and development and increasing inflow of FDI in manufacturing factor ability, capital and power at low cost, a suitable policies for raw material reforms in skill development and above all introduction of full GST for implementations. Section III sheds some lights on the opportunities and challenges relating to the strategies for promoting specific engineering industries in the light of defense sector export promotion market diversification and sale promotion, upgradation of infrastrucher to SSU's and LSU's in export activities, strengthening the brand image of engineering product, international market strategic and so on. The paper puts emphasis that to realize this end, more concerted efforts needs to be strengthen in and reinforce. International marketing strategy. In view of India's current low share of world engineering exports and considerable scope for improvement in its competitiveness, the key imperatives include (i) enhancing the alignment and effectiveness of trade drivers, (ii) boosting the competitiveness of the Indian engineering industry and facilitating upward movement along the value chain, (iii) and strengthening enablers for growth by clearing infrastructural and procedural bottlenecks.

Key words: Enablers, Make In India, GST, Brand Image

Introduction

In the wake of Prime Minister Narendra Modi's Vision to transform Indian Economy towards a Policy Orientation to “Make In India” has apparently raised issues that weather the health of the economy would be gauged by the barometer to “export laid growth” or “growth laid export”¹. With his Make in India campaign, Modi has ushered in a new chapter of hope that Indian has the potential to not only shed the tag of be3ing the world's biggest importer of weapons but also emerge as an export powerhouse. New Delhi spent Rs. 83.458 crore on importing weapons during the last three years. If India has to become a truly global player, the entire nation has to get geared to fact the challenges of competition which in a liberalized system would have more and more competitive and to achieve tangible results, it is necessary to take up four interrelated policy frame, viz., (i) product development and diversification (ii) Target markets for focus and attention (iii) remodeling corporate strategy and planning and (iv) creating export orientation towards non-traditional products especially engineering goods based on their past performance as well as the magnitude of the perceived export potential in which India possesses sustainable competitive advantages on a global scale. The focus has to be areas to be on areas that make economic sense and where Indian is really competitive and skills in the software sector. That's a good place to start².

In the given prospective, an attempt has been made in this paper to examine the market overview and future outlook to the strategies of India's Engineering Sector which is the largest segment of our industry and has a strong capital base, providing more than over 4 million employment to skilled and semi-skilled workers and constitute over 80% of our total industry. If the new government has actually been optimistic to transform the economic under the umbrella of “Make In India” as policy for growth in India's manufacturing sector, it has to laid down a realistic policy for providing a stimulus

for Engineering Industry to develop in product diversification and market expansion along with advance manufacturing technology, larger concessional inflow of capital and relaxation on excise duties and so on. Keeping in view of doing business with confidence across the globe, scaling of up research, innovations and development of infrastructure and harnessing the strength of both the public and private sectors³.

India has a strong engineering and capital goods base. The engineering sector is the largest segment of Indian industry. The important groups within the engineering industry include machinery & instruments, castings, forgings, fasteners, electronic goods and projects exports. The engineering sector employs over 4 million skilled and semi skilled workers. The sector can be categorised into Heavy Engineering and Light Engineering segments. Heavy Engineering constitutes over 80 per cent of the total industry, while light engineering contributes the rest. The heavy engineering industry includes capital goods/machinery and equipment and transport equipment. The light engineering industry includes items like castings, forgings and fasteners and sophisticated micro processor based process control equipment and diagnostic medical instruments. India's manufacturing sector has provided a stimulus for the engineering industry to develop capabilities in product development and advanced manufacturing technology. India manufactures the entire range of industrial machinery. Apart from demand from user industries, the availability of technical education infrastructure that provides an increased number of technically trained human resources, each year has been another key factor aiding the engineering industry in India. The bulk of capital goods required for power projects, fertilizers, cement, steel and petrochemical plants and mining equipment are made in India. This country also makes construction machinery. Equipment for irrigation projects, diesel engines, tractors, transport vehicles, cotton textile and sugar mill machinery. The recent spurt in the domestic construction and infrastructure industry has accelerated the demand for most of the products. India also exports a range of heavy and light engineering goods. India has experienced a steady deepening globalisation and Indian engineering industries are getting integrated into global induction chains particularly after post-liberation period. Belying the considerable gloom that was there about the outlook for Indian engineering exports in a globalised era, the best firms of engineering manufacturing of India have succeeded in realizing rapid growth rates of exports. Infrastructural and procedural inadequacy vis a vis technology upgradation in enhancing the skill levels of workers with labour reform initiative along with greater autonomy for state governments have long been pointed out as sources of competitive disadvantage on items of costs and timelines for Indian exports. Hence, these issues need to be acted on by the government at earliest, so that Indian engineering exports can realise their full potential in real sense in the terms of a solid government push, optimum use of good engineering talent a big bust to the projects with highly skilled work force in software sector to compliment the latest advancement in defense sector⁴.

In the background of these realistic state of conditions to India's engineering exports goods and services in the international market from the point of view of creating more competitive promotion of engineering sector and its continuous management, maintenance, regulation and sustainability, a three prolonged action plan is to be necessary to make some specific step by dividing the aggregative strategy of India's engineering sector into three line of Direction, viz.: (i) Strategy on General Engineering (ii) Strategy to Promote Specific Engineering Industries (iii) Strategy to Promote Engineering Exports⁵.

II. Strategy for General Engineering: Some Emerging Issues

There are essentially two main issues with regard to strategy for general engineering. First, there is an urgent need to expand production of ferrous and non-ferrous metals, if India wishes to develop a strong and vibrant engineering sector. Second, Indian exports of these products are either consisting of raw materials or with low value addition. The emphasis, therefore, should be to move up the value chain. The growth of sectors like electrical machinery, construction, power, telecommunications and automobiles would further create demand of ferrous and non-ferrous metals. The steel sector for instance, is the mother of all user engineering industries⁶.

The main challenge, therefore for the Indian Ferrous and Non-ferrous metals industry is not only to expand capacity but also move up the value chain. The following steps are necessary⁷:

Strategy for Increasing the inflow of FDI in manufacturing sector:

India's market access in engineering related products could be linked to definitive and time bound FDI flows into India;

Preferential incentives may be considered for FDI coming into High Potential products (where the domestic market is almost non-existent). This will ensure a robust export growth as well as lead to the desire technology transfer⁸.

Strategy for improving the Implementation Ratio to encourage Value Addition to Total Investment:

The implementation ratio is reasonably good with respect to Non Ferrous Metals and Transport Equipm (which includes Automobiles and Ancillaries). However, it is rather low in critical segments of the engineering industry, particularly, Electricity.

The Draft on National Manufacturing Policy has made a series of recommendations to National Manufacturing and Investment Zones (NMIZs) for boosting augmentation of manufacturing exports and generation of employment. Hopefully, if this is implemented, there could be a remedy to the problem of low implementation ratio in certain engineering segments and the manufacturing sector⁹.

Formation of Technological Upgradation Scheme for MSME Sector:

Collaborate with the Ministry of MSME on the proposal has been mooted by the Prime Minister's Task Force on Micro Small and Medium Scale Enterprises regarding constitution of a Rs.2500 crore Technology Upgradation Fund Scheme for the Engineering Sector. This will of course help in MSME exporters move up the value chain, both internally and externally. The Capital Subsidy should be increased from 15% to 25% and the loans should be provided up to Rs.5 crore, given the high cost of modern and green technology.

Strategies for Innovational Research and Development:

Research and development are critical driver for higher productivity and economic growth. The country's research orientation in engineering sector is largely demand-driven. A major factor against research and development has been inadequate funding which hampers the completion of research activities. In order to address this imbalance, the Government could initiate activities under four key areas. Viz.;

A R & D mapping exercise for the engineering sector covering the entire spectrum of R & D institutes as well as individual firms.

In order to achieve the above, there is a need to create central coordinating machinery which can initiate the discovery process to encourage and facilitate effective creation, development and marketing of intellectual property/ innovative technology in the engineering sector.

Industry bodies should be encouraged to develop strong partnership among Industry and academic research institutions and end users.

Industry bodies should be urged to lead and act as facilitator to actively commercialize market innovations by adequately developing the R & D institutes as well as the R & D arms for engineering companies¹⁰.

Enhancing these incentives given to investments in R & D to spur the level of R & D activity may be considered as it can provide the necessary momentum for moving up the value chain¹¹.

Provision for availability of credit at Low cost:

The “All in cost ceilings” which includes rate of interest, other fees and expenses in foreign currency except commitment fee, pre payment fee, and fees payable in Indian Rupees should be lowered to 1.5% from the present 3% to 5% for average maturity period of over 5 years for these non corporate exporter members. This means that for non corporate exporter borrowers the interest rate should be Libor (London Inter Bank interest rate) plus 1.5% for loan maturity of 3 years to 5 years and Libor plus 3% for maturity of loans of over 5 years.

Strategy for Improving the availability of Power:

India has a chronic shortage of electricity and ranks below all other similar countries on quality of power. Shortage and poor quality of electricity supply has led to reliance on more expensive forms of power generation. Some of the steps that may be considered are:

Increase investment in power generation and transmission capacities beyond the current five year plan by encouraging merchant and captive power plants to bridge the huge gap between demand and supply,

Continue privatization of distribution to tackle losses and improve operational efficiency through increased investment in the necessary infrastructure.

Suitable Politics for Raw Materials:

Suitable policies to provide engineering raw materials like steel, pig iron and other non ferrous metals at international prices, particularly to the MSME and the light engineering sectors, may be formulated. This is required because the MSME units do not import raw materials as they find it uneconomical to import.

Strategy for Labour Reforms and Enhancement of Skill Development:

The existing labour laws are not in line with the current recessionary market realities. Some of the amendments that may be considered are:

Removal of ambiguity from the Contract Labour (Regulation and Abolition) Act, 1970. The 1970 Act may be retained but Section 10 tightened up so that ambiguity about continuance of contract labour and absorption following abolition is removed.

Amend Section V B of the Industrial Disputes Act for easier exit option for firms without adversely the interests of labour.

Similarly with the advent of new technology in the engineering sector, there is a crying need for skill upgradation. According to various estimates of different industry bodies, the engineering sector faces a skill shortage of nearly 30% in certain high skilled segments and anything between 10-15% in the low to medium scale segment. Industry expects that this shortage is likely to widen in the next couple of years. The role of National State Development Corporation (NSDC) is critical. The Engineering Industry Bodies and leading companies should draw up action plans for the development of skills for the general engineering industries, which are tailor made for these industries and make the trainees employable¹².

Introduction of Full GST for Implementation:

The GST should be introduced at the earliest. Further the GST should be a full GST so that all taxes, be it at the Centre or State Level, are included in the GST scheme. Also one GST should be introduced across all States and the rates

should become under the GST system. This will reduce the cascading effects of indirect taxation both at the Centre and State Level¹³.

III. Strategy for promoting specific Engineering Industries: Opportunities and Challenges

The strategy must be built up as two pronged action, plan i.e.(a) the strategy of Automobile industry in general and (b) Auto Components in particular.

The strategy for Automobile Industry:

The Indian auto industry has recently started penetrating international market and is working towards increasing its presence in various countries across the world. There is need for strengthening five interrelated strategies for promotion of auto industry for more penetration in international market such as :

Post Infra structure Creation of two dedicated berth for handling automobile export cargo, one on the East coast preferably in Chennai and the other on the West coast, each equipped to handle output of 5 lakh vehicles annually by 2015¹⁴.

Earmark space for parking, vehicle repair at these ports to accommodate at least 20,000 vehicles at a time – like the proposed multi level facility at Chennai port.

for better handling of automobile export cargo and the multi level facility for earmarking space for parking.

MAT (Minimum Alternate Tax) to be waived for export earning of exporters

Negotiation of Quota system with compelling countries for automobile market access.

American for long term finance through, EXIM Bank or other Govt. institutions for vehicles exports either bulk or retail exporting.

There is a need for policy interventions and technological road map to highlight Hybrid and Electric vehicles for Indian automotive industry to achieve global technology leadership. There is also an urgent need to Technology Upgradation & Development Scheme (TUDS) for Auto Components.

The long term competitiveness of the auto component industry in India is a major concern, as is the ability of the industry to invest in technology upgradation, especially in case of the SMEs. The investment is required not only for auto components but also for the casting industry on which the industry is dependent. Moreover, improvements by investing in appropriate technologies that allow for efficient production, testing and validation will also lead to cost competitiveness¹⁵.

Defense Sector

India's defense sector budget is expected to grow at a rate of 8% till 2014, with an anticipated capital budget share of 45% which includes procurement of aircrafts and aerospace equipments such as, heavy and medium armament systems, vehicles, platforms and naval vessels among others. The balance is accounted by revenue expenditure, which caters to the operating expenditure of the three services (Air Force, Army and Navy) and other Departments for spares, stores, fuel etc. It is estimated that 17% of the revenue expenditure (9% of total defence budget) will go towards spare parts manufacturing. Thus, the total manufacturing opportunity in defence is 54% arising from capital budget (45%) and revenue budget (9%) translating into a market of approximately US \$ 91 billion for the period 2010-2014.

To realize this potential, the following steps are suggested:

The issue of FDI in defence has many dimensions. Thus FDI should be considered as an important element in expanding the manufacturing capabilities in the defence sector in the country and liberalization of FDI rules in this sector could take place in phased manner.

The Ministry of Defence (MoD) should come out with a short term procurement plan on a regular basis for finalizing domestic/foreign collaborators. This will help the domestic private sector realize its anticipated potential.

Currently, the offsets policy is applicable to any procurement that is above Rs.300 crore in value. The threshold for offset should be reduced to Rs.75 crore in line with what is practiced in other countries to ensure participation from a larger breadth for the domestic industry.

The tenure for Banked offsets clause, which has been recently introduced, should be increased to around 5 years.

III. Strategy for Export Promotion of Engineering Products: Recent trends and future dimensions:

Establishment of separate Export Processing Zone:

There is strong need for establishing separate engineering exports processing zones and export oriented units. A few engineering items with highest potential have to be selected for development in these special processing zones. The locations of the export processing zones are to be identified where there is a large concentration of these items. Establishment of separate zones for engineering products will enable them to overcome the problems of infrastructure and raw materials shortage. In addition it can attract more foreign direct investment into the production and export of engineering products.

Selective Approach for market diversification and sales promotion:

For prioritizing commodities, to be selected for export production: we have concentrated on too much products while most of our competitors. For instance, China, Mexico, Korea, Hungary, Czechoslovakia have concentrated on few exports products. They have emerged as fastest growing engineering export countries it is observed that 85 per cent of engineering exports have contributed by fewer product categories as compared to that of India. Facing numerous problems due to lack of raw material and infrastructural deficiencies, most of engineering units can hardly match overseas requirement in terms of technology quality and cost. In the light of the above, we must concentrate on selected thrust products market mix and give them a full policy package and incentives and other contemporary input required for export production. For furthering the export of engineering products, India must evolve an aggressive sales promotion effort. It can be done through advertisement, trade fairs, specialized trade fairs, brand promotion. Along with the sales promotion effort, strict adherence to delivery schedules is crucial for the success of Indian engineering exports. Further, after sales services and customer care effort is highly indispensable for the smooth growth of engineering exports. Therefore Indian engineering exports have also to rigorously follow the after sales services and customer care support. This can be accomplished by customer care centre and providing incentives to overseas collaborations.

Adequate Support to Export Credit and upgrading infrastructure to SSUs and LSUs In Exports Activists –

Small scale engineering exports still constitute around 40 per cent of total engineering exports. For the continued contribution of these units to the exports sector, they must be provided with the production and exports incentives, support for adoption of latest technology, advisory services and market support to sustain the competition in the international market. Although exports can be increased by providing incentives to small scale industrial units (SSI) units,

there is limit to growth. There is a need for involving large units in exports activities. The exports intensity figure is still very low in India especially for large units. Hence, it is necessary to gradually increase the exports intensity ratio of Indian products by involving more and more large scale units and exporting more from the existing units. We must explore the possibility of setting up Free Trade Area/Preferential Trade Agreement with other countries where our exports have largest concentrations. Another area which needs special emphasis is establishment of joint ventures and foreign collaborations in engineering production. It is also imperative to attract more foreign direct investment into the engineering sector¹⁶.

Thus, the promotion of exports relating to both SSI and LSI must be built up through a compressive policy to be stable with reference to incentive structure thrust focus, market penetration efforts and procedural issues. Efforts must be made to limit on more on more paper work as well as the arbitrary fixation of shipping freight rates for exports. So that they can concentrate on marketing their products in the international market. They have been persistent complaints from the exporting community particularly, engineering exporters regarding the arbitrary fixation of freight rates in shipping liners time to time. Hence, there is an urgent need for formation of a National Shipping Regulator. In this context, the Draft Shipping Trading Practices Bill 2010 is a welcome step that deals with arbitrary shipping trade practices¹⁷.

Besides this, for engineering exports, freight rate contribute anything between 25% - 30% of total costs of exporting and therefore 1 port inefficiencies directly impinge on the export competitiveness of engineering exports from the countries. Thus deepening of draughts at berths, Anytime working in ports, deployment of shore mobile cranes for engineering cargo, etc. are the need of the hour.

(iv). Promotion and Strengthening of Brand Image of Indian Engineering Products:

A large number of countries around the world are facing credit problems in wake of the global crisis. However, some of these countries have also pushed through stimulus packages targeting the infrastructure sector. If, India could provide lines of credit to these countries, it may be possible for Indian engineering companies and exporters to supply such infrastructure related goods to these countries. Prime minister of India has already started this process for African Countries. This may be extended to some Latin American Countries. To promote engineering goods of the SME sector, India needs to go to diversified markets and more emphasis should also be given to the Latin American Countries. For this purpose, there should be, at least three INDIA SHOWS specialized for engineering goods and services whereby Export Promotion Councils and industry Bodies can take at least 150 Indian companies to diversified markets.

(v). International Marketing Strategy and the Future of INDIA'S Engineering Exports:

Engineering exports from India have grown considerably in the last few years with a growth rate which has been much higher than the world average in view of the accelerated growth, a new Strategy Paper, titled Growth of Engineering Exports' commissioned by Engineering Export Promotion Council (EEPC) and carried out by Ernest & Young, has set a target of USD 110 billion by 2014 for total engineering exports. While releasing the Strategy Paper, Anand Sharma, Union Minister of Commerce and industry said, "This indeed, is a robust target and if engineering is able to maintain its share of nearly 22% in total exports then by 2014, India's total exports should be in the range of USD 500 billions.

The global economic recession is likely to leave its imprint for some more time, particularly in the developed world and hence it is important that our exporters concentrate on two critical ingredients for future growth, to remain competitive so as to maintain quality and also to diversify into new markets.

The revival engineering exports in 2010-11 in the aftermath of a negative 19% growth in 2009-10 and the dispersal of engineering exports to hither to untapped counties during 2010-11 indicate the contribution of schemes like Focus market Scheme (FMS) Focus Product Scheme (FPS) and the Market linked Focus Product Scheme (MLFPS) in promoting engineering exports from the country. Since there is a likelihood of world demand slackening in the next couple of years

and the revival may have happened with a lag, it is felt that these export promotion schemes should be expanded and strengthened to boost competitiveness of our engineering goods.¹⁸

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To realize this end, more concerted efforts need to be put in international marketing strategy. In view of India's current low share of world engineering exports and considerable scope for improvement in its competitiveness, the key imperatives include (i) enhancing the alignment and effectiveness of trade drivers, (ii) boosting the competitiveness of the Indian engineering industry and facilitating upward movement along the value chain, (iii) and strengthening enablers for growth by clearing infrastructural and procedural bottlenecks.

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